

Supplementary Material for "GPAS: Multi-Objective Genetic Programming with AUC and Separability Measures for Multiclass Classification"

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1 Introduction

This is the Supplementary Material for the paper entitled "GPAS: Multi-Objective Genetic Programming with AUC and Separability Measures for Multiclass Classification". It includes two sections: one compares GPAS with six traditional Machine Learning (ML) algorithms, and the other provides an experimental comparison of using the first quartile versus alternative transformation references, including the mean, the median, and the minimum output values of GP classifiers on the training set.

2 Comparison of GPAS with six traditional ML methods

To evaluate the performance of our proposed GPAS method against other traditional ML algorithms, we compared GPAS with six algorithms: k-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Decision Tree (DT), Naive Bayes (NB), Neural Network (NN), Support Vector Machine (SVM), and Random Forest (RF) [3]. All of these algorithms are implemented based on the scikit-learn library [2] using default parameters. Table. 1 shows the comparison results between GPAS and the six traditional ML algorithms.

As shown in Table. 1, GPAS only achieves the best performance only on the Cmc and Cle datasets. However, on the other datasets, GPAS consistently ranks among the top-performing methods, demonstrating its robustness. As illustrated in Fig. 1, GPAS attains the second-best overall rank, only slightly behind RF. It is worth noting that RF is an ensemble-based method, whereas GPAS is a non-ensemble approach. Despite this, GPAS achieves comparable performance. In addition, GP-based methods are capable of discovering relationships among features and possess implicit feature selection capabilities, which provide a certain degree of interpretability [1]. The literature [1] reports the relationship between interpretability and performance for several machine learning algorithms, indicating a trade-off between the two. GP-based methods are considered highly

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Table 1. Comparison of GPAS with six traditional ML algorithms.

Dataset	Method	Mean	Std	Dataset	Method	Mean	Std
Tae	KNN	41.39	6.95	Cle	KNN	21.23	2.32
	DT	62.96	6.57		DT	29.80	3.14
	NB	52.50	6.88		NB	31.75	4.72
	NN	46.91	5.48		NN	29.43	3.67
	SVM	36.88	6.58		SVM	20.00	4.28
	RF	59.72	7.20		RF	30.49	4.01
	GPAS	56.50	4.40		GPAS	32.72	3.95
Movement	KNN	70.87	4.07	Ecoli	KNN	63.53	2.79
	DT	65.28	5.07		DT	52.75	7.46
	NB	62.33	3.34		NB	52.78	4.95
	NN	70.60	3.45		NN	35.48	4.95
	SVM	76.35	3.52		SVM	64.36	1.65
	RF	79.35	4.17		RF	61.05	5.40
	GPAS	72.60	4.26		GPAS	61.54	5.11
Vehicle	KNN	64.74	2.63	Cmc	KNN	48.34	1.89
	DT	69.81	2.69		DT	45.08	1.96
	NB	45.94	3.28		NB	49.53	2.16
	NN	64.12	4.30		NN	52.50	2.12
	SVM	49.39	2.50		SVM	44.46	1.60
	RF	75.05	2.10		RF	49.58	1.87
	GPAS	72.94	2.74		GPAS	54.12	1.87
Segment	KNN	93.56	0.73	Waveform	KNN	81.25	0.99
	DT	96.08	0.71		DT	73.99	1.01
	NB	79.69	1.08		NB	80.13	0.63
	NN	93.73	1.24		NN	83.49	0.90
	SVM	85.92	1.09		SVM	86.92	0.82
	RF	97.48	0.41		RF	85.25	0.83
	GPAS	88.31	1.59		GPAS	85.94	0.74

interpretable, second only to DT. Notably, the proposed GPAS achieves performance close to RF while retaining relatively high interpretability, demonstrating a favorable balance between model performance and interpretability.

3 Comparison of GPAS with different transformation references

To demonstrate the effectiveness of the reference-based label prediction method in GPAS, we compared the results of using the median, mean, and minimum output values of the training samples from the GP classifier as reference points. The comparison results are shown in Table 2.

As shown in Table 2, GPAS achieves the best performance on the Tae, Cle, Movement, Ecoli, Cmc, and Segment datasets, while maintaining competitive results on the Vehicle and Waveform datasets. Furthermore, as illustrated in Fig. 2,

Fig. 1. Post-hoc test results for Table 1. Connected classifiers are not significantly different (at $p = 0.05$).

Table 2. Comparison of GPAS different transformation references.

Dataset	Method	Mean	Std	Dataset	Method	Mean	Std
Tae	Median	46.00	4.93	Cle	Median	31.38	2.73
	Mean	48.19	6.71		Mean	30.97	2.35
	Last	48.89	7.38		Last	31.00	4.28
	GPAS	56.50	4.40		GPAS	32.72	3.95
Movement	Median	67.48	8.03	Ecoli	Median	61.20	5.51
	Mean	66.88	8.51		Mean	61.21	5.40
	Last	65.07	6.67		Last	57.00	6.37
	GPAS	72.60	4.26		GPAS	61.54	5.11
Vehicle	Median	72.65	2.24	Cmc	Median	53.75	1.56
	Mean	72.72	2.68		Mean	54.14	1.17
	Last	73.92	1.99		Last	52.84	0.65
	GPAS	72.94	2.74		GPAS	54.12	1.87
Segment	Median	87.56	1.96	Waveform	Median	85.87	0.32
	Mean	87.62	1.93		Mean	85.85	0.35
	Last	76.57	4.63		Last	83.82	2.44
	GPAS	88.31	1.59		GPAS	85.94	0.74

Fig. 2. Post-hoc test results for Table 2. Connected classifiers are not significantly different (at $p = 0.05$).

GPAS attains the best overall performance ranking. These results demonstrate the effectiveness of using the first quartile as the reference point.

References

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